

TEACHING MEDICAL COMPOUND WORDS WITH INTERACTIVE METHODS

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[**https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8423905**](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8423905)

Annotation: *In this article are discussed that using interactive method is to create an environment for active, free thinking of the student by creating the most favorable conditions for the learning process. It demonstrates its intellectual potential, and enhances the quality and effectiveness of learning.*

Key words: *interactive method, active, free thinking, favorable, conditions intellectual potential, compound words, pedagogical technologies.*

The role and influence of Latin language in the field of medicine today are gaining a higher speed in the world as well as in Uzbekistan. The main factors for this phenomenon include expanding medical terminology with the world after gaining the independence and increasing speed and scope of information exchange in the global village. Medical terminology is a strong motivation to learn Latin through the English for those who wish to promote their global competences. The main goal of the interactive method is to create an environment for active, free thinking of the student by creating the most favorable conditions for the learning process. It demonstrates its intellectual potential, and enhances the quality and effectiveness of learning. The interactive lesson is organized in such a way that in the process no student is left out, that is, they have the opportunity to openly express their views on what they see, know and think. Not every opinion expressed by students, whether it is right or wrong, will be criticized. They can exchange knowledge and ideas. The following are the most effective ways to engage your students through interactive teaching methods and interactive teaching styles.

Brainstorming is one of the interactive teaching methods which demand performance in group sessions. With this process, students are able to develop creative thoughts and ideas. The method helps learners to pull learn together.

Online interaction such as chat, forums and email Team-idea mapping, group passing, individual brainstorming, structured and unstructured, reverse or negative thinking, nominal group relationships.

OSTEOLOGIA-the study of the structure and function of the skeleton and bony structures. It is joined by two words: OSTEO-O-LOGIA. The vowel joining it is "O". "OSTEO" means-bone "LOGIA" means-science,study

NEUROLOGIA- the scientific study of the nervous system and the diseases that affect it. It is joined by two words:NEURO-O-LOGIA The vowel joining it is "O ". "NEURO" means-nerve "LOGIA" means-science,study

TOMOGRAPHIA- imaging by sections or sectioning that uses any kind of penetrating wave. It is joined by two words:TOMO-O-GRAPHIA The vowel joining it is "O ". "TOMO"means-concerning to layer,layer in rentgennology

"GRAPHIA" means-the process of recording

SALPINGECTOMIA-a surgical procedure where one or both of a woman's fallopian tubes are removed. It is joined by two words:SALPINGO-ECTOMIA

"SALPINGO" means-uterine tube "ECTOMIA" means-surgical operation for removal of some organ or tissue

LAPAROTOMIA-a surgical incision into the abdominal cavity. It is joined by two words:LAPARO-O-TOMIA The vowel joining it is "O ". "LAPARO" means-abdomen "TOMIA" means-surgical operation for incision, opening of some organ

HYDROTHERAPIA-also known as aquatic therapy or water therapy, is the practice of using water as therapy. It is joined by two words:HYDRO-O-THERAPIA The vowel joining it is "O ". "HYDRO" means-water,fluid "THERAPIA" means-treatment(not surgical)

CHIROSCOPIA- the science which deals with the study of the prints of the palms of the hand. It is joined by two words:CHIRO-SCOPIA

"SCOPIA"means-instrumental examination

SPONDYLODYNIA-pain in a vertebra. It is joined by two words:SPONDYLO-O-ODYNIA The vowel joining it is "O ". "SPONDYLO"means-vertebra "ODYNIA" means-pain,sence of pain

PYLOROSTENOSIS-a narrowing of the opening from the stomach to the first part of the small intestine (the pylorus). It is joined by two words:PYLORO-STENOSIS "PYLORO"means-pyloric body of stomach "STENOSIS" means-stenosis(narrowing)

HEMOLYSIS- breakdown or destruction of red blood cells so that the contained oxygen carrying pigment hemoglobin is free into the surrounding medium. It is joining by two words : HEM-O-LYSIS The vowel joining it is "O" "HEMO" means blood "LYSIS" means destruction

CARDIOSCLEROSIS-narrowing of heart caused by formation of fibrous tissue in the cardiac muscle. It is joined by two words: CARDIO-O-LOGIA The vowel joining it is "O" "CARDIO" means heart "SCLEROSIS" means narrowing

BRONCHIOECTASIA- enlargment of the bronchiol due to excess mucus that can make the lung more vulnerable to infection It is joined by two words "BRONCHI-O-ECTASIA" The vowel joining it is "O" "BRONCHIO" means bronchiol "ECTASIA" means enlargment of the hollow organ

BLEPHAROPTOSIS- a condition where the upper eyelid droops. It is joined by two words : "BLEPHARO-O-PTOSIS The vowel joining is "O" "BLEPHARO" means eyelid "PTOSIS" MEANS displacment of the organ downward

Conclusion: I have came to the following conclusion. The theory of new pedagogical technologies allows the formation of compound words, allowing medical students to

acquire through knowledge in a short period of time. Although initial experience has been gained in the application of new pedagogical technologies in the teaching of compound words, they do not adequately meet the requirements of the time.

Development of theoretical and practical bases of the organization of teaching of compound words on the basis of interactive methods in medical universities provides efficiency of activity of these educational institutions.

To sum up, everyone has an understanding, resources and interests which can be utilized. Teachers play an important role in assessing learners, engaging their understandings, correcting misconceptions. It is a responsibility of teachers to put their full efforts to help students easily catch and perform well in class.

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